

IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN TEACHING PROCESS

Khodjaniyazova Soniya Maratovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434962>

Abstract. Choosing and utilizing the correct educating approach is a critical thought for all language teachers. To get it right and understudies advance towards familiarity at pace in a calm and pleasant learning environment. Therefore, this article describes importance of communicative language teaching in teaching process.

Keywords: communicative language teaching, communication, teaching strategy, social obstructions.

Communicative language teaching too employments bunches or sets for exercises, which permits for collaboration to be ingraining within the language-learning classroom. Bunch work or work in sets permits for understudies to discuss, hone, and ace fabric without feeling confined within the prepare of learning a unused dialect. Frequently times, understudies who work together will feel more comfortable practicing familiarity over the botches they make in their grammar. This guarantees that understudies are in educational process to get to be familiar within the modern language through collaboration, where understudies may learn from one another and work together. The communicative approach employments apparatuses, and innovation for a personalized learning approach as well. Each understudy learns differently and has diverse interface, so through CLT, instructors can make learning more individualized to best meet the requirements of their understudies. For illustration, understudies may appreciate talking approximately sports or prevalent culture, so the educator may inquire understudies to examine those ranges with one another through different exercises, such as role-playing real-life scenarios, bunch discourse or combine discourse, among other different exercises that empower collaboration. Communicative language strategies are right now a well known point of discourse and their adequacy in building students' familiarity and communication abilities have been taken into consideration by language instructors all over the world. As is to construct language teaching tools that offer assistance instructors to form a more speaking-based dialect classrooms and offer assistance their understudies to create stronger communication abilities, communicative language teaching as one of the foremost viable and imperative language educating procedures right now.

Communicative language teaching strategy risen within the 1980s as a reaction to the developing request for a language educational modules that would empower learners to utilize the moment language in real-life circumstances. Already, outside language teaching (or English language instructing for non-native English speakers) has transcendentally had its accentuation on syntactic competence, especially because grammar-translation was the foremost acknowledged instructing strategy, instead of really centering on creating students' communication and interaction aptitudes. Language does mainly exist to form communication conceivable. CLT strategies basically center on the interaction amid a classroom-based outside dialect lesson or farther dialect learning session, in which dialect learners really deliver speech and lock in discussions for most of the classroom time utilizing the target dialect. The most reason behind communicative language educating strategies is to get ready understudies to be sure communicators completely different real-life settings, through tedious verbal hones and student-student participation.

Each understudy in a language classroom has students' needs, levels of capacities, and interface. Hence, having distinctive assignments planned to meet desires and abilities of diverse understudies is basic in Communicative language teaching. Moreover, giving a steady learning environment makes interest simpler for understudies, particularly those who effectively feel modest around dynamic interest. Some challenges that instructors may confront when actualizing this strategy in their language classrooms are:

1. Large course sizes: CLT is most viable in littler bunches where understudies can effectively used in communicative exercises. In large classes, it can be challenging to oversee and encourage significant interaction between all understudies and the teacher's time might not be adequate to supply criticism and bolster for all understudy pairs/groups.
2. Restricted assets: Actualizing CLT may require extra dialect learning assets, such as true materials, audio-visual helps, or advanced instruments. Lacking get to to these resources can ruin the compelling application of CLT within the classroom.
3. Understudy desires: A few understudies might have a conventional see of dialect learning, anticipating a center on language structure and lexicon. They may be safe to the communicative approach or feel baffled by the accentuation on speaking-based exercises.

4. Social obstructions: In a few societies, understudies may be reluctant to talk up or lock in in communicative exercises due to societal norms, inhibitions, or concerns almost making botches before their peers.

5. Evaluation challenges: Traditional language evaluations and exams frequently center on perusing, composing and language structure abilities instead of communicative competence. Instructors may discover it troublesome to assess students' advance in a way that adjusts with the objectives of CLT and they might have to be spend additional time updating their evaluation and examination forms.

Communicative language teaching incorporates learning with a clear reason, cultivating a student-centered approach, expanding understudy engagement, advancing lesson inconstancy and imagination, and creating all center dialect aptitudes. Instructors in a communicative language teaching classroom take on parts as facilitators, guides, and co-communicators, improving the learning encounter for understudies. In spite of the various points of interest, it's critical to consider the challenges or confinements of CLT when deciding in case it's the proper approach for your particular setting.

Used literatures:

1. Robert J. Morzano "Classroom management that works" Virginia USA, - 2003
2. Donald Ary, Lucy Cheser Jacobs, Chris Sorensen - "Introduction to Research in Education" - © 2010, 2006 Wadsworth, Cengage Learning USA
3. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF CLIPPINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". - 2023. - T. 2. - №. 2. - C. 145-149.
4. <https://sanako.com/applying-communicative-language-teaching-approach>